

Ninth Data Release of the DESI Legacy Surveys Available at the Astro Data Lab

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on behalf of the DESI Legacy Imaging Surveys & Astro Data Lab teams

The DESI Legacy Imaging Surveys Data Release 9 (LS DR9) is publicly available through the [Astro Data Lab](#), and we invite the community to use its products, including images and catalogs. This release marks the official imaging dataset for target selection for the ambitious cosmological survey being conducted with the Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI);[1],[2]).

Begun in 2014, the [Legacy Imaging Surveys](#) are a combination of three imaging surveys and archival data covering more than

The Legacy Imaging Surveys project was unusual in three ways. First, it introduced a novel approach to data collection: it implemented a dynamic observing strategy, where each frame was analyzed for seeing, throughput, and depth as soon as it was taken, and exposure times of future observations were adjusted accordingly [4]. Second, the LS team pioneered a new cataloging technique (“the Tractor,” created by Dustin Lang) where the sky was “forward modeled” (i.e., in each region of sky, unique models for each source were derived by fitting all of them simultaneously to all the individual sky

Figure 1. From top to bottom: LS DR9 color image in the combined *grz* bands, the DR9 Tractor model of the same region of the sky, and the DR9 residual map (image minus model) shown with enhanced brightness and contrast to highlight faint features. To interactively explore this region, visit the [Sky Viewer](#) around RA=215.1137 and Dec=0.9736
Credit: Legacy Surveys/D. Lang (Perimeter Institute)

20,000 square degrees of extragalactic sky in the *g*, *r*, and *z* bands [3]. The survey data were obtained using the Dark Energy Camera (DECam) on the Víctor M. Blanco 4-meter telescope at Cerro Tololo, the Mosaic-3 camera on the Nicholas U. Mayall 4-meter telescope at Kitt Peak, and the 90Prime camera on the Steward Observatory’s Bart Bok 2.3-meter telescope. Beyond the primary goal to produce a uniform dataset for the selection of DESI targets, the imaging and catalog data enable a very wide diversity of astrophysics projects. They are already being used in studies of faint stars, stellar streams, faint ultra-diffuse galaxies, gravitational lenses, high redshift quasars, and galaxy clustering.

images [5]). The result is a two-dimensional model of the sky in each band (Figure 1). Third, the project was executed as a completely public endeavor: all data taken for the survey, all data products, and all the software (for observation planning, scheduling, data reduction) were made available publicly as the survey was in progress. The project published eight data releases in five years.

LS DR9 includes not only data from the 3 surveys described above (the DECaLS Survey, NOAO Proposal IDs 2014B-0404 and 2016A-0190; the MzLS Survey, 2016A-0453; and the BASS Survey, 2015A-0801) but also archival images

from the [NOIRLab Astro Data Archive](#) from other projects, most notably public data from the Dark Energy Survey (DES) project. LS DR9 also reports mid-infrared photometry measured at 3.4, 4.5, 12, and 22 microns by NASA’s WISE satellite for all optically detected sources. The mid-infrared photometry was measured (using the LS source positions and shapes as priors) from the single-band unWISE coadds [6] which includes data from the original WISE survey and the NEOWISE phase of the WISE mission. The LS DR9 footprint covers over 20,000 square degrees (Figure 2) and reaches depths (in AB magnitudes) of $g=24.7$, $r=23.9$, $z=23.0$, $W1=20.72$, and $W2=19.97$. The survey is notable for its uniformity across its footprint, lending itself to cosmological analyses.

The data products from the survey are available through NOIRLab’s [Astro Data Lab](#) and through the [Legacy Surveys project website](#). In addition to the main Tractor photometric catalog, DR9 also includes single-epoch forced photometry catalogs, which report photometry from each individual image that contributed to the survey, as well as a photometric redshift catalog [7]. Astro Data Lab provides users with Python and Table-Access-Protocol (TAP) interfaces to these data as well as [web-based queries](#) and [Jupyter notebooks](#). A new scientific example notebook demonstrates an

investigation of large-scale structures using photometric redshifts to augment the census of member galaxies in spectroscopically identified overdensities such as galaxy clusters and superclusters (Figure 3). Astro Data Lab users can easily join the LS DR9 catalogs with other holdings such as catalogs from Gaia, WISE, or selected Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) spectroscopic and photometric tables.

The imaging surveys can be explored visually using the [Imagine Sky Viewer tool](#), written by Dustin Lang, which includes views of the stacked images, the Tractor models, and the residual maps and provides the ability to download FITS and JPEG cutouts. Various catalogs of astrophysical interest (e.g., Gaia DR2, SDSS spectroscopy, DESI target lists) can be overlaid on the images.

The Legacy Imaging Surveys project is the result of the efforts of an international team working together to create one of the largest and most uniform surveys ever conducted of the night sky (see the project [acknowledgments](#)). Support was provided by the National Science Foundation, the Department of Energy’s Office of Science, Steward Observatory, the Chinese Academy of Sciences, and partner universities around the world, including staff at three observatories and observers

Figure 2. Sky map showing the >20,000-square-degree coverage of LS DR9 (g,r,z bands in blue, z -band only in red). The footprint avoids regions of high dust attenuation displayed by the underlying dust map, which is the darkest along the Galactic Plane. DESI spectroscopy will target the region north of declination -30 degrees.
 Credit: A. Raichoor/EPFL/LBL and the DESI Collaboration

Figure 3. Large-scale galaxy overdensities from LS DR9 photometric redshifts clearly show several clusters and filaments (blue color map), and the most prominent features correspond to the presence of red sequence galaxies with spectroscopic redshifts (red dots). This analysis is conducted in one of the latest [Jupyter notebook](#) scientific examples available to all Astro Data Lab users. Credit: S. Juneau/NOIRLab and the Astro Data Lab team.

who traveled to Kitt Peak and Cerro Tololo to collect the data. The initial detrending of the data was performed at NOIRLab in Tucson, and the cataloging and data analyses used the substantial computing resources of the [National Energy Research Scientific Computing Center](#). This team has now shifted its gaze to the next horizon: using the DESI instrument at the Mayall telescope to obtain 30 million galaxy redshifts and nearly 10 million stellar spectra. Together, the Legacy Imaging Surveys and DESI will represent one of the largest cosmic cartography projects ever attempted.

DESI saw first light in October 2019 and was fully commissioned in 2020 (Figure 4). The Survey Validation phase took place in early 2021, yielding over one

million successful redshifts even before starting its five-year survey on 17 May 2021. DESI's ambitious survey aims to measure the expansion history of the Universe over the last 10 billion years and provide measurements of cosmological parameters with unprecedented precision. As probes of the expansion of the Universe, DESI has selected four classes of extragalactic targets: bright ($r < 19$) galaxies that lie primarily at low-redshift; luminous red galaxies, the progenitors of present-day ellipticals; emission line galaxies; and quasars. The DESI target lists, selected from LS DR9, will also be publicly accessible through Astro Data Lab.

While we wait for DESI spectroscopy to open new vistas into the cosmos, the Legacy Imaging Surveys imaging data are ready for exploration.

References:

- [1] [DESI Collaboration, et al. 2016a, arXiv:1611.00036](#)
- [2] [DESI Collaboration, et al. 2016b, arXiv:1611.00037](#)
- [3] [Dey, A., et al. 2019, AJ, 157, 168](#)
- [4] [Burleigh, K., et al. 2020, AJ, 160, 61](#)
- [5] [Lang, D., Hogg, D. W., & Mykytyn, D. 2016, Astrophysics Source Code Library](#)
- [6] [Meisner, A. M., et al. 2019, PASP, 131, 124504](#)
- [7] [Zhou, R., et al. 2021, MNRAS, 501, 3309](#)

Figure 4. Comparison of SDSS DR16 (top) and DESI (bottom) spectra (taken during commissioning) and three-band color images for the same galaxy (gr_i bands for SDSS; grz bands for DESI). Only spectral regions around typical emission lines of interest are shown. The LS data are deeper with better image quality than SDSS, and the DESI spectra have higher spectral resolution and signal-to-noise ratio. Images span 20 arcseconds on a side. Credit: R. Pucha/University of Arizona, S. Juneau/NOIRLab, and the DESI Collaboration